

THE TREND OF SENTIMENTALISM IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Xamidova Kamola

Namangan State University

1-st year master's degree Faculty of English Literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5889203>

Abstract: Sentimentalism is a practice of being sentimental, and thus tending toward basing actions and reactions upon emotions and feelings. As a literary mode, sentimentalism has been a recurring aspect of world literature. Sentimentalism includes a variety of aspects in literature, such as sentimental poetry, the sentimental novel, and the German sentimentalist music movement, European literary sentimentalism arose during the Age of Enlightenment, partly as a response to sentimentalism in philosophy. In eighteenth-century England, the sentimental novel was a major literary genre. Its philosophical basis primarily came from Anthony Ashley Cooper, 3rd Earl of Shaftesbury, a pupil of John Locke. This trend of literature considers the process of ideas, images and plots drawn from the literatures of the East, to which they were exposed by the uniqueness of the philosophical and aesthetic consciousness of the 18th century.

Key words: sentimentalism, 18th century, writers and their works.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the importance of our people's perfect knowledge of foreign languages can scarcely be exaggerated as our country aspires to win a decent place in the word community, because our people see their great future as an in mutual accord and cooperation with their foreign partners. However, it is necessary to remember always that the study of foreign languages should not be carried out at the expense of oblivion to the mother tongue. It is hard to understand and justify a specialist, especially one holding a high post, who is unable to choose fine and appropriate words to express his idea, concisely and precisely, in his mother tongue.

This article discusses the problems of sentimentalism and works of English. Since the works of the enlighteners considered of the work, obviously gravitate toward the union of the artistic principle with a philosophical and even scientific approach to reality, one more urgent task of the work was to illuminate the processes of the influence of scientific knowledge on subjects, ideas and partly on the artistic peculiarities of the literature of the 18th century. We consider the study of the processing of ideas, images and plots drawn from the literatures of the East, to which they were exposed by the uniqueness of the philosophical and aesthetic consciousness of the 18th century. This is due to the fact that any

culture, let alone a degree of maturity, as in our case, approaches the development of another culture selectively and creatively.

Actuality of the theme is the problem learning the works of English writers and analyses by criteria of literature. And actuality is determined by learning and comparing sentimentalism of European literature. The problems of using non-technical and technical aids in developing speech skills and sub-skills, selecting teaching aids according to the types of speech, the methods of using teaching aids in developing speaking skills, listening skills, reading skills and writing skills which can be further developed life-long, depending on the individual needs. The aim of the article is to define the stages, forms and features of mastering the eastern theme in the English prose of the 18th century, revealing its creative results.

THE ORIGIN AND SOURCES OF SENTIMENTAL LITERATURE IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

1.1. Effect of social life and condition to the origin of new literary trend

Emerging in England in the mid- to late eighteenth century, and reflecting a similar trend in continental literature at the time, literary sentimentalism or "sensibility" prioritized feeling. It developed primarily as a middle-class phenomenon, reflecting the emphasis on compassion or feeling as a desirable character trait in the newly emergent middle class. Although, on the one hand, the reader might take pleasure in feeling itself, in England by the 1770s the rise of sensibility was also linked to a growing activism-the awareness of and concern for the suffering of others reflected in, for example, the antislavery movement, concerns about child labor, and the campaigns for better hospitals, prison reform, and charity schools as well as in the response to the suffering associated with the rapid rise of industrial capitalism and the urban misery caused by exploitative labor practices. The word "sentimental" is first known to have appeared in print in English in the 1740s. Becoming almost immediately popular, the term was used to describe the emotional state of a sensitive and "genteel" person, and sentiment began to play an important role in literature. As Louis Bredvold notes, "Drama and fiction had discovered that pathos could best soften the heart and raise the tear that betokens humanity". Among the earliest British novels that heralded the rise of sentimentalism were Samuel Richardson's *Pamela; or, Virtue Rewarded* (1740) and *Clarissa* (1747-1748); Oliver Goldsmith's *The Vicar of Wakefield* (1766); Laurence Sterne's *A Sentimental Journey* (1768); and Henry Mackenzie's *The Man of Feeling* (1771). According to Paul Langford, Mackenzie's novel was a "deliberate attempt to portray the sentimentalist as a benevolent man". To be a

"man of feeling" became a desirable goal even among middle-class men of business.

The sentimental novel first made its way across the Atlantic in the form of the seduction narrative. After William Hill Brown's *The Power of Sympathy* appeared in 1789, Susanna Rowson's (1762-1824) *Charlotte Temple* (1794) became America's first bestseller. Rowson's novel inspired feeling, and generations of readers, men and women from all classes, wept over the hapless Charlotte's fate. As Cathy Davidson points out, it is a mistake to think of the novel as only sentimental. Subtitled *A Tale of Truth*, it portrays an all-too-common and very realistic situation: the seduction and betrayal of an innocent and ignorant young girl and her subsequent death in childbirth. Addressing the young female reader, Rowson assures her that, as Davidson notes, "she is not alone in a world in which she has no legal or political identity". As Rowson says in her preface, compassion inspired her to write the novel, and she hopes that her words will help to prevent some of the miseries that she chronicles. During certain periods in American history, sentimentalism has been particularly evident in literature. One such period was the Progressive Era of the late nineteenth to early twentieth centuries, during which, as Jaime Harker points out, the "muckrakers" used a sentimental appeal to feeling in order to bring about social and economic reform. Upton Sinclair's 1905 novel *The Jungle*, for example, vividly portrays moving scenes of the miserable working and living conditions of immigrants in the unregulated meat-packing industry. Essentially a middle-class movement, Progressivism was promoted by Protestant ministers, and Progressives often used religious rhetoric to attack the injustices of industrial capitalism.

To survey the history of sentimental literature in America is to gain insight into some of the most critical moments in American culture. As Thomas Paine's influential essay of 1776 explained, it is on the grounds of "common sense" that the colonial Englishman would be able to "generously enlarge his views beyond the present day" and so imagine and ultimately fight for independence.

And the existence of common sense, Paine and his audience understood was proved by the recognition that all people respond to the loss of their children in the same way. Sentimentality—featuring broken homes restored, dying children revived, and lost lovers found through the power of shared emotions—is a way to remind readers that at root we are all lost children, no matter how vast may seem the differences made apparent by logic and circumstance. Sentimentality expresses the utopian impulse to abolish boundaries and expand community upon which the ideological force of American identity depends. In other words, it

is a term for a discursive mode, not a genre nor a historical period, that is used to construct a shared or common sensibility that hides the traces of its invention under the cloak of tradition.

The language of sentiment what Walt Whitman called the “dialect of commonsense” may no longer direct Americans toward revolutionary political action; however, it certainly continues to inform American narrative, oratorical, and visual discourses in contemporary films, political speeches, and both popular and monumental visual arts. The continued power of sentiment in America is due to its important role in both defining what it would mean to be an American and establishing the process by which one could become an American during the years between the Revolutionary War and the close of the Civil War.

Sentimentalism is not confined to written works, and the discussion that follows could deal with visual, electronic, and aural as well as literary sentimentality. Even in the period focused on here, the mode of sentiment was dominant in nonliterary representations such as painting and sculpture, and even in landscape design. This definition adds sentimentality to the limited set of major expressive modes that includes irony, tragedy, romance, realism, and comedy. Sentimentality is the set of symbolic gestures used to shape common sense through the simultaneous deployment of both conservative and generative impulses. These gestures operate on three axes: topic, diction, and rhetoric to facilitate and even to enforce a collaborative effort against loss by engaging the subject and the object of sentiment in a constitutive economy of donative presentation and re-presentation. The three signal topics of sentimentality are lost homes, lost families, and broken bonds.

The mere representation of these topics, however, does not in itself call for the adjective “sentimental”. The sentimental mode also depends on the use of a distinctive vocabulary and rhetoric to present these topics. The defining vocabulary is a highly embellished, “literary” lexicon appropriated from recognized sources and mortared together with the diction of vernacular language.

Neither the presence of these topics nor the use of this language, however, demands the term “sentimental” unless a particular rhetorical trope, the apostrophe, is also present. Apostrophe, whether a direct address to an abstraction or one to an absent person, dramatizes the existence of multiple registers of imagined reality. Apostrophic address, in combination with certain topics and language, is the defining symbolic gesture of sentimentality because it is the vehicle through which the viewer or reader is encouraged to participate in

the violation of these apparent planes of representation in order to reconstruct newer ones.

Despite what critics now recognize as the pervasiveness of sentimentality in American culture, the adjective “sentimental” has had dual valences – celebratory and pejorative – since it entered the lexicon in the eighteenth century. By 1776, Paine did not have to explain how it was that morality derives from those human faculties that allow us to share a common sensibility with one another. This idea had already become a critical commonplace supported in different ways by the ideas of Continental philosophers such as Jean-Jacques Rousseau and Emmanuel Kant and of British thinkers as various as Lord Shaftesbury, Adam Smith, and Francis Hutcheson. Whether in the register of fiction or in the register of political philosophy, Britons throughout the empire were increasingly exposed to a persuasive moral and aesthetic appeal to a shared common sensibility that was characterized by a feeling of loss. Thus, the novelist Samuel Richardson asked his reader to enter into sympathy with the parents of his heroine, Pamela, as Pamela asked her parents to enter into sympathy with her, and the philosopher Adam Smith asked his reader to believe in the recursive power of personal empathy to control the atavistic tendencies of the marketplace.

The problem that the sentimental mode addresses – how to create and perpetuate community once the traditional bounds of blood and geography have been loosened – was posed by Adam Smith in the *Theory of Moral Sentiments* (1759) as a problem of epistemology concretized as a problem of communication. Since our own senses “will never carry us beyond our own person,” we have to rely on something else. That something else, Smith explained, is imagination. Imagination allows us to communicate outside ourselves through a curious process of “representing to us what would be our own case, if we were in the case” of another, even while we understand that it is the “impressions of our own senses only, not those of his, our imaginations copy”. Smith, writing in the first flush of a truly mass culture brought about by the proliferation of cheap printed matter, was able to theorize the distinguishing paradox of sentimentalism: somehow, through the copying of our own impressions, we can generate new sensations that will in turn change the very nature of the feeling self. The imaginative reproduction of feeling allowed for an economy that in turn permitted the growth of this sentimental capital. “Right feeling,” rather than appeal to an extrinsic source such as the Bible, became the standard measure of authentic moral judgment, and therefore of moral action.

However, the idea that feelings could be communicated only through representation raised the possibility and problem of counterfeiting, which has continued to color theoretical responses to the power of sentiment. Karen Haltunnen, for example, has traced the anxiety caused by the need of nineteenth-century Americans to distinguish authentic from sham sentiment. This anxiety, Haltunnen argues, is further evidence of the degree to which emotional force was valued. Especially within the American context, then, the term “sentimentalism” has generally been used to dismiss representations that seem to evoke an unwarranted emotional response. Walt Whitman, though celebrating the power of emotional imagination to allow him to experience and speak for the “Maternal as well as the paternal, a child as well as a man,” was careful to describe himself as “no sentimentalist.”

As scholarly attention to American literary history increased during the twentieth century and attempts were made to sort the literary heritage of the previous century, the question was posed as to whether the sensational designs of sentimentality [Jane Tompkins’s term 1985] were warranted, and when and by whom they might be legitimately employed. James Baldwin, in his seminal essay of 1949, *Everybody’s Protest Novel*, persuasively argued that there is no warrant, aesthetic or moral, for the literary mode that dominated the previous century. Baldwin pointed out that the antirationality of sentimental identification, of common sense, is the basis for mob action, and that neither the reactionary power of mobs nor that of sentiment can be controlled. Like F. O. Matthiessen before him in the revolutionary study *The American Renaissance* (1941), Baldwin considered that the unambiguously political power of sentimentality conflicted fatally with any aesthetic claims that might be made for it. In fact, as Herbert Ross Brown’s 1940s study, *The Sentimental Novel in America (1789-1860)* typifies, it was difficult for twentieth-century artists and cultural critics not to see “sentiment” and “aesthetics” as mutually exclusive terms.

Two developments in academic criticism of the late twentieth century fueled a revision of the term and the literature to which it refers. One was the historical recovery of the literary works produced by nineteenth-century women and black Americans. This ongoing project, though a conventional form of literary scholarship, is inspired by contemporary political needs to counter claims of the insignificance of women and blacks to the cultural history of America. The other development was a shift in formalist criticism toward a poststructuralist methodology that makes qualitative criteria part of the object of study. The very number of recovered works by “dis-remembered” nineteenth-century authors

that could be described as “sentimental” testified to a poetics that was escaping current critical appreciation.

To use Jane Tompkins's term, many of these works clearly had “sensational designs” upon their readers, with dead babies, whipped slaves, and empty hearths depicted in what seemed to be an awkwardly overwrought manner.

But whereas an earlier generation of critics stopped at this realization and therefore felt justified in looking away from the many traces of a literary culture in which women and blacks fully participated, a newer generation struggled to “re-remember” how to understand this large body of work. The critical questions then became “What are the codes governing sentimentality, and how do they function in particular contexts?” In other words, critics have begun to attempt to articulate the ways in which sentimental literature fulfilled some criteria of beauty, and the ways in which it served some criteria of purpose.

1.2. Sentimentalism as an independent literary style, features and forms

The nature and status of sentimentality is widely contested, though most critics would agree that the adjective “sentimental” is applied to works that have a primary appeal to the emotions and operate by means of affect. Sentimental literature is interested in the experience, display, effect, and interpretation of emotion and in stirring up emotion in readers. The literature and culture of sentimentality has traditionally been viewed as clichéd, predictable and of limited aesthetic and social value. Yet critical work in the last two decades – primarily in the fields of literary and cultural studies, but also in philosophy – has attempted to rehabilitate the historical sentimental tradition and to argue for the inclusion of sentimental works in the canon. Sentimental philosophy is firmly rooted in 18th-century Britain, and the consequent explosion of sentimental literature meant that the long 18th century is the locus of most critical work in the field of sentimentality. The second most important period in this respect is 19th-century America: American literature and culture has attracted outstanding critical work. Studies of 19th-century British literature and culture lag behind, though several important reassessments of Victorian sentimentality do exist.

Recent critical studies of Victorian sentimental texts and contexts tend to draw heavily on the arguments and approaches developed by critics of 18th-century British and 19th-century American sentimental culture. For this reason, although this bibliography focuses on Victorian sentimentality, it also includes critical studies that do not concentrate explicitly on British Victorian texts but have significant implications for their study and have been influential in the field. Victorian sentimentality touches on broad issues of sensibility – including medical

and physiological studies – and emotion, which can be profitably summed up under the general heading of affect.

The form of the American domestic and sentimental novel developed in the late 18th and early 19th century.

Drawing on 18th-century British novels that tended to privilege affective relations, such writing became associated with women writers in the 19th century through the rise of “separate spheres” ideology.

This ideology was always a middle – class and often a white phenomenon that encouraged the gendered identification of work with men and home with women. During the 19th century, women writers in the United States often coupled the anti-Enlightenment emphasis on emotion with domestic plots that spoke to the power of feelings to effect right action. Popular with women readers, domestic novels written in the sentimental style tend to feature a young girl protagonist who must depend on her moral compass to guide her through an immoral world, a path that frequently leads to marriage. Literature that evoked a sentimental response to a particular injustice became identified with women co-opting sentimental conventions to shine light on social problems. The most popular American novel of the 19th century, Harriet Beecher Stowe’s *Uncle Tom’s Cabin*, used sentimentality to address the evils of slavery. Sentimental literature was also often associated with Christianity and or forms of Christian benevolence applied to reform movements. Much of the reform literature addressed itself to developing a model of citizenship that dovetailed with class mobility, assuming the goal of middle-class belonging. Despite the sentimental genre’s contemporary popularity, it was later discriminated against as conventional.

The most popular American writers of domestic and sentimental fiction included Lydia Maria Child, Maria Cummins, Catharine Maria Sedgwick, E. D. E. N. Southworth, and Susan B. Warner. J. Hector St. John de Crèvecoeur’s *Letters from an American Farmer* (1782) exemplifies the eighteenth-century attempt to trace the sentimental process by which one “becomes an American.” Only by “leaving behind him all his ancient prejudices and manners,” explains Crèvecoeur’s *American Farmer*, can a person enter into the free and mutual embrace that constitutes American identity. This identity, Crèvecoeur wrote, depends not on political or geographical boundaries that can be determined by logic and analysis of factors outside the self, but on the nature of one’s feelings. In fact, the *American Farmer* ends his narrative by explaining the necessity of removing himself and his family beyond the borders of the new United States in order to preserve the conditions necessary to maintaining his feelings of “Americanness.”

In Letters from an American Farmer, as in Thomas Paine's various responses to the American crisis, sentimentality is a way of freeing the self so that it can enter into the liberal relationships on which the new society can be built.

In the years of the early republic, both authors and the subjects they addressed reflected the transatlantic nature of American identity, which depended on sentimentality to help liberate American from British culture.

Only later would writers turn the power of sentiment toward the problem of defining or limiting the nature of American culture. This was as true for writers of fiction and poetry as for essayists like Paine and Crèvecoeur. *Charlotte: A Tale of Truth* (1791) by Susanna Haswell Rowson (ca. 1762-1824) is a good example of what a novelist popular in America at that time would call the "power of sentiment." Born in England, Rowson spent time as a child on both sides of the Atlantic before choosing to become a paragon and proselytizer of American identity. *Charlotte* was written and first published in England but found its best audience in America, where, as the literary historian Cathy Davidson has traced, it attracted readers from all social classes, regions, and religions. Thematically, the story dramatizes a contest between sham and true feeling that makes a shambles of numerous homes over several generations. The recognition of common feeling repeatedly establishes voluntary communities in the form of families that must continually struggle against the tyrannical threat of the indulgence of selfish feelings.

Set during the years of the Revolutionary War, the main story concerns a young girl, Charlotte, who responds to the unsolicited affection of a thoughtless British officer, Montraville, by abandoning her own family to follow him to America. There, Charlotte is herself abandoned, but not before giving birth to an illegitimate daughter. This daughter, like the new nation she is born in, will have to establish an identity within a network of voluntary relationships because the story of her mother has shown how unreliable legal and blood relationships can be. Although it is not a typical eighteenth-century epistolary novel, in *Charlotte* the circulation of letters plays an important role in the plot as well as in the discourse.

Through letters, the characters are able to address other characters despite geographical distance, and the narrator is able to redirect the reader's attention by shifting both the object and subject of focus. The language in the letters, no matter which character is supposed to have authored them, differs dramatically from the normative language of the narration and is distinctive to each fictional

author. As extended apostrophes, these letters force the reader to exercise imaginative flexibility.

The circulation and the obstruction of affections through letters drive the plot: Montraville seduces Charlotte through a letter that the young girl knows she should not have accepted; Montraville prevents the delivery of letters from Charlotte to her parents; the cad Belcour prevents Charlotte's letters to Montraville from being delivered; a letter of dismissal from Montraville breaks Charlotte's heart; and finally, the successful delivery of a letter to her parents allows for a deathbed reconciliation.

Rowson's novel typifies the sentimental novels that were read in the America of the early Republic. The signature sensationalism of sentimental literature in America is seen in Rowson's focus on the plight of unwed women, or rather, on the difference between legitimate and illegitimate affective associations. Her narrator explicitly asks her readers to "reflect how many errors we are ourselves subject to" before condemning "those unhappy women who fall victims to guilt and folly." But it also asks her readers to discriminate between kinds of feelings, because some reinforce community while some are antithetical to it.

Rowson herself chose America as a place to become what she felt she had always been. She celebrated its potential in a number of popular plays, such as *The Female Patriot* and *The Columbian Daughter*. The feelings that are claimed to be most natural and most common – love of parents and love of children are the ones that are most revolutionary and therefore to be fostered in the new nation. The feelings that are produced through the force of tradition or money or physical strength can only betray.

CONCLUSION

Almost a hundred-year history of the existence of works on oriental themes in European literature of the 18th century, a large number of their editions and reprints allows us to talk about their regular appearance in various European literature and independence from literary fashion. Philosophical and satirical journalism and moralizing works on oriental themes were born in English, as in other European literatures, in response to the philosophical and aesthetic demands of the era that in fact opened the East. The substantive originality of English works on oriental themes is determined by the socio-historical peculiarities of the literary process in this country.

The regularity of the profound interest of the Enlighteners towards a different culture and art is conditioned by the gravitation of their worldview

towards universalism in the approach to the history and problems of human studies. It is characteristic in the respect that there was more information about the East in the XVIII century. Oriental literature developed precisely in the Enlightenment. In the XVIII century, the selective approach of scientists and travelers to the image of the East was brightly manifested, where they sought and found confirmation of the idea of the universal character of the mind. The origin of Eastern themes in European literature, and through it the recognition of the equality of culture and art of the East in the world community of reason has an important humanistic meaning.

The European perception of the XVIII century of the phenomenon of Oriental cultures began primarily in the system of philosophical knowledge, but at the same time attempts are made to develop it aesthetically which do not cease throughout the century, are strengthened in the 1960s and qualitatively new character at the turn of the XI century. If one cannot talk about the complete equality of the philosophical and aesthetic levels in the approach of the Enlightenment to the theme of the East, the latter is still quite important in their aesthetic search and creative practice. Objectively, the efforts of enlighteners and pre-Romantics to shape their forms and means, developed by the Oriental literature, led to a change in the notions of artistic and non-fiction, sometimes contrary to the views of the authors themselves, influenced the narrative art of the eighteenth century. The Eastern form gave a certain freedom to the authors both in terms of content and in stylistic experiments. In a broader sense, works on oriental themes in European literatures are in the mainstream of trends to update them at the expense of the overcoming of the canons of classicism, in the new historical conditions, which are becoming a brake on the development of art.

The achievements of Eastern literatures enriched European literature to a certain extent, giving them a new source of spectacular stories, visual aids and even vocabulary, which confirms the idea of the reciprocal character of literary relations between the West and the East.

Due to the fact that the works on the oriental theme had a clear orientation on philosophical and ethical and journalistic problems, they most fully reflected the features of artistic thinking of the 18th century, are inextricably linked with philosophical and scientific knowledge, and experienced their influence at all levels of their structure. In the consciousness of the 18th century art and science are inextricably linked, not without reason, many of the greatest writers of the era were prominent scientists (Montesquieu, Diderot, Goethe), somehow recruited their forces in science (Goldsmith, Johnson, Smollett).

Works of oriental themes in European literatures of the 18th century are not self-contained. In the selective approach to the eastern theme of not only enlighteners, but pre-romantics and romantics, the creative character of the interrelationships and mutual influences of the world's literatures has clearly manifested itself, which do not amount to a mechanical sum of borrowings.

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